

Comparative Analyses of Hamstring Tightness and Sitting Duration Among Professional and Non-Professional Drivers in a Nigerian Community

O.E. Ayeni ✉

Department of Occupational Therapy, Faculty of Medical Rehabilitation, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria

M.A. Olayemi

Department of Medical Rehabilitation, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria

A.T. Onigbinde

Department of Physiotherapy, Faculty of Medical Rehabilitation, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria

T.F. Kekere

Department of Prosthetics and Orthotics, Faculty of Medical Rehabilitation, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo State, Nigeria

S.C. Ayinla

Department of Prosthetics and Orthotics, Faculty of Medical Rehabilitation, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study investigated the prevalence of hamstring tightness among male professional, non-professional and non-drivers in a Nigerian community. It also compared the hamstring tightness of the three classes of participants.

Ethical clearance was granted for the study. The design was a mixed-method of cross-sectional and comparative designs. Convenience sampling technique was used to select 150 participants who are commercial drivers (professional), private car owner who drives (non-professional) and non-drivers. Fifty individuals were recruited for each class. The hamstring tightness of the participants was determined using the Active Knee Extension Test (AKET) which was measured in degrees. Descriptive statistics and Inferential statistics of Paired t-test, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to analyse the data obtained. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

The result showed that only 16% of the non-drivers had hamstring tightness while 78% and 54% of the professional and non-professional drivers were with hamstring muscle tightness in both lower limbs. The hamstring muscle tightness was significantly higher among the driver than non-drivers ($p = 0.000$) and the non-professional drivers ($p = 0.015$). The driving experience of the professional drivers (18.90 ± 6.06 years) was significantly higher than that of non-professional drivers (6.08 ± 4.13 years), ($t = 81.538$, $p = 0.000$). The duration of sitting of the professional drivers was significantly higher than that of the non-professional drivers and non-drivers ($F = 74.39$, $p = 0.000$). There was no significant relationship between BMI and prevalence of hamstring tightness across the groups.

In conclusion, the prevalence rate of hamstring muscle tightness was higher in professional than non-professional drivers and non-drivers. Also, the duration of sitting was significantly higher among the professional driver.

Introduction

Hamstrings are made up of three muscles, namely, semi membranous, semitendinosus and both long and short

heads of Biceps Femoris [1]. The muscle complex occupies the posterior compartment of the thigh and it is made up of three individual muscles that originates

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at the pelvis, run posteriorly along the length of the femur, crossing both the femoroacetabular and tibiofemoral joints excluding the short head of the biceps femoris that takes off from the lateral lip of the femoral linea aspera, distal to the femoroacetabular joint [2]. Amongst these muscles, the semimembranosus and semitendinosus are the least injured while the short head of Biceps femoris is commonly involved in injuries [1]. The hamstrings perform flexion of knee and extension of hip [3].

Hamstring tightness is known as the inability to fully extend the knee while the hip is flexed, which thus creates discomfort or pain along the region of the hip and knee in posterior compartment of thigh [4]. Inability to achieve greater than 160 degrees of knee extension when the hip is flexed to 90 degrees is considered as hamstring tightness [5]. There is hamstring Muscle tightness when the knee extension angle becomes greater than 20 degree [6]. Hamstring muscle decreases the absorption of force, affects posture, the range of motion of lower extremities and increased the possibility of developing Low Back Pain [7].

The hamstring muscles are attached to tuberosity of ischium which is a part of posterior aspect of pelvis. Hence, tightened or shortened hamstring muscles affect the low back resulting to Low Back Pain (LBP) [8,9]. The tightness is linked with increased hamstring muscular strains and is also known to have association with low back pain [10]. Muscle tightness is not only the cause of reduced range of motion of the lower limb joints; it also leads to various musculoskeletal problems [11,12]. The tightness is caused by a decrease in the ability of the muscles to deform, resulting in reduced range of motion at the joint on which these muscles are inserted, leading to hamstring injuries [12]. In recent times, it has been documented that hamstring tightness could be linked with obesity, prolonged driving or sedentary daily routine [13]. There are three grades of hamstring injury depending on severity [14]. Grade 1 is a mild muscle pull or strain while Grade 2 (moderate) is a partial muscle tear and a complete muscle tear is Grade 3 (severe). The hamstrings performance dropped because of pain, tightness and this also affects occupational performance [15].

There are different methods to assess hamstring tightness, Straight Leg Raising (SLR), Active Knee Extension (AKE) and Passive Knee Extension (PKE) tests [16]. The active knee extension test is performed within the pain free range of subject's range of motion [17]. More recent studies showed that active knee extension was the most efficient tool for measuring hamstring tightness as it prevented pelvic rotation [18]. In addition, passive knee extension is always performed by the examiner without considering the potential effect of gravity on the tested leg [19].

There are different reports on the prevalence of hamstring tightness in different occupations but there are scanty reports on that of drivers [20,21,5,22]. Furthermore, there are speculations that hamstring inextensibility may lower dynamic stability and therefore increase the risk of injury [23]. In Nigeria, few reports available are limited to apparently healthy individuals [21]. There is also dearth of report on the relationship between BMI and hamstring tightness while there are little or no report on comparative analysis of Hamstring tightness among different classes of drivers. The objectives of this study were to investigate the prevalence of hamstring tightness among the non-drivers, professional and non-professional drivers and also compare the tightness.

Materials and Methods

The participants in this study were professional and non-professional drivers, and non-drivers living within the Ile-Ife community in Osun State, Nigeria.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Included are intra-city commercial drivers that were being paid for driving services within the community (Professional) and private car owners who were driving their personal cars (non-professionals). Also included are those that were not involved in driving any form of car (non-drivers).

Study Design

This study was a cross-sectional survey but there was a comparative analysis of the hamstring tightness. The study sites were two locations in the community namely, motor parks and homes of participants.

Sampling techniques

Convenience sampling technique was used to recruit 150 participants using the sample size equation of Jaykaran et al [24]. The population size computed for each group was 50 participants to make up a total of 150 participants for the three groups.

Instruments

The height and weight were measured using height metre and bathroom weighing scale respectively while Body Mass Index (BMI) was computed (kg/m^2). The hamstring tightness was measured using goniometer (Active Knee Extension [AKE] angle) and a proforma questionnaire was used to obtain demographic data and other vital information such as the age, years of driving experience, duration of driving and rate of involvement in road traffic accident.

Procedures

The ethical approval was granted by the Health Research and Ethics Committee of the Institute of Public Health (HREC), College of Health Sciences, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. All the participants signed an Informed Consent form. The Active Knee Extension (AKE) test was performed using the standard procedure. Each participant laid on a foldable 2-inches student size bed in supine position

with both lower extremities extended and the joint axis marked. Both anterior superior iliac spines were in alignment. The lower extremity not being measured was stabilized by the examiner at the lower third of the thigh. The participants were told to actively raise their legs as high as 180°, the participant’s knees remained extended while they kept their foot relaxed and held in position for about 5 seconds. A standard universal goniometer was then placed over the previously marked joint axis, and the goniometer arms were aligned along the femur and fibula. The Active Knee Extension measurement was defined as the degree of knee flexion from terminal knee extension. Each knee extension was measured twice, and the average value of the AKE test was used for analysis.

Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics of mean and Standard Deviation was used for the demographic variables. Paired t-test was used to compare the Hamstring tightness of the right and left lower limbs of the participants. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to compare Hamstring tightness of the three groups. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Results

The result of the study showed that the mean age of the non-drivers was 25.92 ± 4.97 years while the mean age of the professional drivers was 40.84 ± 6.99 years and that of the non-professional drivers was 29.08 ± 7.10 (Table 1). The BMI and its classification are presented in tables 2 and 3. The result of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showed that there were significant differences in the ages of the participants (F=

74.85, p= 0.000), (Table 4). The result of the Post Hoc Tests showed that the ages of the professional drivers and non-professional drivers were significantly higher than that of the non-drivers (p= 0.000, p= 0.015) respectively (Table 5). The mean of the participants are presented in table 1. The result of Analysis of variance showed that there were no significant differences among the heights of the professional drivers, the non-drivers and the non-professional drivers (F= 2.104, p=0.126), (Table 4). Furthermore, there was significant difference in the weights between professional drivers and the non-drivers (p=0.001). Also, there was significant difference between the body weights of non-professional drivers and non-drivers (p= 0.010). The result of the Post-Hoc Analysis (LSD) showing the trend of significance differences are presented in table 5.

The result of the study showed that the mean years of driving experience among the professional drivers was 18.90 ± 6.06 years. Similarly, the mean years of driving experience among the non-professional drivers was 6.08 ± 4.13 years as presented in Table 6. The result of the t-test showed that there was significant difference in driving experience between the professional and non-professional drivers in the study (t= 81.538, p= 0.000). The results of the mean duration and comparison of sitting and accident rates are presented from tables 7 to 10. Furthermore, the result of the Post Hoc Tests showed that there was significant difference in the driving experience across the three groups (p= 0.000), (Table 7).

Table 1: Age and Selected Anthropometric Parameters of the Participants

Participants	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Age: ND	19.00	39.00	25.92	±4.97
PD	28.00	56.00	40.84	±6.99
NPD	21.00	45.00	29.08	±7.10
Height: ND	1.56	1.85	1.72	± 0.07
PD	1.62	1.80	1.75	± 0.05
NPD	1.60	1.83	1.75	± 0.08
Weight: ND	50.00	80.00	64.46	±7.04
PD	53.00	85.00	70.66	±5.82
NPD	52.00	94.00	65.84	±13.15

Key: SD= Standard Deviation; ND= Non-drivers; PD= Professional Drivers; NPD= Non-professional Drivers

Table 2: Mean Body Mass Index of all the Participants

BMI CLASSES	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
ND	17.30	27.00	21.86	±2.06
PD	15.20	29.40	22.94	±2.57
NPD	15.40	28.90	22.78	±8.22

Key: SD= Standard Deviation; ND= Non-drivers; PD= Professional Drivers; NPD= Non-professional Drivers; BMI= Body Mass Index

Table 3: Body Mass Index Classification of all Participants

Participants	(BMI)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
ND	Underweight	1	2
	Normal	44	88
	Obese	5	10
PD	Underweight	1	2
	Normal	38	76
	Obese	11	22
NPD	Underweight	11	22
	Normal	33	66
	Obese	6	12

Key: ND= Non-drivers; PD= Professional Driver; NPD= Non-professional Drivers; BMI= Body Mass Index

Table 4: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Comparing the Demographic Characteristics Across the Groups

Variables	ANOVA	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	p-value
Age	Between Groups	6181.49	3090.74	74.84	0.00
	Within Groups	6070.08	41.29		
	Total	12251.57			
Height	Between Groups	1603.57	801.78	2.10	0.12
	Within Groups	55643.60	381.12		
	Total	57247.18			
Weight	Between Groups	1060.14	530.07	6.21	0.00
	Within Groups	12551.77	85.38		
	Total	13611.92			
BMI	Between Groups	33.89	16.94	0.65	0.53
	Within Groups	3844.40	26.15		
	Total				

Key: F= Frequency; BMI= Body Mass Index; p= level of significance

Table 5: Post Hoc Test Results Comparing the Demographic Characteristics Across the Groups

Variables Dependent	Groups(I)	Groups(J)	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	p-value
Age	1.00	2.00	-14.92*	1.28	0.00
		3.00	-3.16*	1.28	0.01
		1.00	14.92*	1.28	0.00
	2.00	3.00	11.76*	1.28	0.00
		1.00	3.16*	1.28	0.01
		3.00	-11.76*	1.28	0.00
Height	1.00	2.00	-7.00	3.92	0.99
		3.00	0.34	0.39	0.77
		1.00	-6.97	3.92	0.99
	2.00	3.00	7.00	3.92	0.07
		1.00	6.97	0.92	0.07
		3.00	-6.20*	3.92	0.07
Weight	1.00	2.00	-1.37	1.84	0.00
		3.00	6.22*	1.84	0.45
		1.00	4.82*	1.84	0.00
	2.00	3.00	1.38	1.84	0.45
		1.00	-9.92*	2.12	0.00
		3.00	3.92	2.12	0.06
BMI	1.00	2.00	-1.08	1.02	0.29
		3.00	-0.92	1.02	0.37
		1.00	1.08	1.02	0.29
	2.00	3.00	0.16	1.02	0.87
		1.00	0.92	1.02	0.37
		2.00	-1.58	1.02	0.87

Key: 1.00= Non-drivers; 2.00= Professional Drivers; 3.00= Non-professional Drivers; Std. Error= Standard Error; p-value= level of significance

Table 6: Duration of the Driving Experiences of the Professional and Non-Professional Drivers

Driving Experience	Minimum (yrs)	Maximum (yrs)	Mean (yrs)	SD	T	p
PD	6.00	28.00	18.90	±6.06	81.538	0.000
NPD	1.00	15.00	6.08	±4.13		

Key: SD= Standard Deviation; PD= Professional Drivers; NPD= Non-professional Drivers; yrs= Years; F= Frequency; p= level of significance

Table 7: The Duration of Sitting Hours among the Participants

Sitting Hours	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	F	P
*ND	2.00	10.00	4.98	±3.29	74.39	0.000
PD	8.00	18.00	13.44	±2.28		
NPD	2.00	12.00	4.92	±5.60		

Key: SD= Standard Deviation; ND= Non-drivers; PD= Professional Drivers; NPD= Non-professional Drivers; p= level of significance

Note: *Sitting at work place

Table 8: Frequency Distribution of Involvement in Accidents among the Professional and Non-Professional Drivers

Accident	No of Times involved in accident	Frequency	Percentage (%)
ND: Not Involved	–	6	92.0
	1		8.0
PD: Not Involved	–	11	22.0
	1	5	10.0
	2	15	30.0
	3	6	12.0
	4	6	12.0
	5	3	6.0
	6	4	8.0
NPD: Not Involved	–	34	68.0
	1	7	14.0
	2	4	8.0
	3	4	8.0
	4	1	2.0

Key: PD= Professional Drivers NPD= Non-professional Drivers

Table 9: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Comparing the Driving Experience, Sitting Hours and Accident Rates Across the Groups

Driving	ANOVA	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	p-value
Experience	Between Groups	4388.41	2194.20	81.53	0.00
	Within Groups	3175.41	26.910		
	Total	7563.83			
Sitting hours	Between Groups	2371.00	1185.50	74.38	0.00
	Within Groups	2278.97	15.93		
	Total	4649.97			
Accident rates	Between Groups	22.63	11.31	6.09	0.00
	Within Groups	103.91	1.85		
	Total	126.54			

Key: F= Frequency; p= level of significance

Table 10: Post Hoc Test Results Comparing the Driving Experience, Sitting Hours and Accident Rates Across the Groups

Driving	Groups (I)	Groups (J)	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	p-value
Experience	1.00	2.00	-10.42	1.35	0.00
		3.00	2.39	1.34	0.07
		1.00	10.42*	1.34	0.00
	2.00	3.00	12.82*	1.03	0.00
		1.00	-2.39	1.34	0.07
		3.00	-12.82*	1.03	0.00
Sitting hours	1.00	2.00	-8.46*	0.81	0.00
		3.00	0.06	0.81	0.94
		1.00	8.46*	0.81	0.00
	2.00	3.00	8.52*	0.79	0.00
		1.00	-0.06	0.81	0.94
		3.00	-8.52*	0.79	0.00
Accident rate	1.00	2.00	-1.97*	0.71	0.00
		3.00	-0.94	0.76	0.22
		1.00	1.97*	0.71	0.00
	2.00	3.00	1.04*	0.40	0.01
		1.00	0.98	0.76	0.22
		3.00	-1.04*	0.40	0.01

Key: 1.00= Non-drivers; 2.00= Professional Drivers; 3.00= Non-professional Drivers

Note: Std. Error= Standard Error; p-value= level of significance

Only 11 (22.0%) professional Drivers had not been involved in any accident while 39 (78.0%) had been involved in Road Traffic Accident (RTA), once or more. The result also showed that 34 (68.0%) of the non-professional drivers had never been involved in any RTA. Similarly, 16 (32.0%) of the non-professional drivers had accident once or more, as shown the (Table 8). The result of the Analysis of variance showed that there were significant differences in the accident rates of the participants ($F = 6.098, p = 0.004$), (Table 13). The result of the Post Hoc Tests showed that the accident rates experienced by the professional drivers was significantly higher than that of the apparently healthy individuals ($p = 0.008$) and the non-professional drivers ($p = 0.013$). Also, there was no significant difference in the accident rates between the non-professional drivers and the apparently healthy individuals ($p = 0.223$), (Table 10).

The result showed that among the non-drivers, the Active knee extension test was less than 20° (No hamstring tightness). The mean Active knee Extension (AKE) for the right and left limbs are $164.98^\circ \pm 7.5$ and $164.82^\circ \pm 8.3$ respectively. The result of the paired t-test showed that there was no significant difference in the hamstring tightness of the right and left hamstring

muscle of the non-drivers ($t = -0.247, p = 0.806$), (Table 14). There are 42 (84.0%) and 43 (86.0%) without hamstring muscle tightness in the right and left limbs respectively among NPD (Table 11). The prevalence of Hamstring Tightness in the right and left lower extremities among Professional and Non-professional Drivers are presented in table 12.

Among the professional drivers, only 15(30%) and 11(22.0%) were without hamstring muscle tightness in the right and left limbs respectively. Also, 9(18.0%) and 10 (20.0%) of the professional drivers had mild hamstring muscle tightness in the right and left limbs respectively. The mean Active knee Extension (AKE) for the right and left limbs were $152.62^\circ \pm 9.1$ and $150.98^\circ \pm 9.7$ respectively. The result of the paired t-test showed that there was significant difference in the hamstring muscle tightness of the right and left limbs ($t = -2.362, p = 0.022$), (Table 13). The mean Active knee Extension (AKE) of the NPD for the right and left limbs are 157.57 ± 12.7 and 154.90 ± 12.0 respectively. The result of the paired t-test showed that there was significant difference in the hamstring tightness of the right and left hamstring muscle ($t = -2.253, p = 0.025$), (Table 13).

Table 11: Prevalence of Hamstring Tightness among the Non-drivers in the lower extremities

Hamstring muscle	Lower Extremities	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No Tightness	Right	42	84.0
	Left	43	86.0
Mild Tightness	Right	1	2.0
	Left	—	—
Severe Tightness	Right	7	14.0
	Left	6	12.0

Table 12: Prevalence of Hamstring Tightness among Professional and Non-professional Drivers

Drivers	Hamstring Tightness	Lower Extremities	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Professional	Absent	Right	15	30.0
		Left	11	22.0
	Mild	Right	9	18.0
		Left	10	20.0
	Severe	Right	26	52.0
		Left	29	58.0
Non-professional	Absent	Right	23	46
		Left	23	46
	Mild	Right	4	8.0
		Left	5	10.0
	Severe	Right	23	46.0
		Left	22	44.0

Table 13: Results of the Comparison of the Right and Left Hamstring Tightness among all the Participants

	Active knee Extension (AKE)°	Hamstring* Tightness	SD	t	p
ND: Left limbs	164.8°	15.2°	8.29	-0.25	0.81
Right limbs	165.0°	15.0°	7.46		
PD: Left limbs	150.9°	29.1°	9.73	-2.36	0.02
Right limbs	152.6°	27.4°	9.12		
NPD: Left limbs	155.3°	24.7°	12.97	-2.25	0.03
Right limbs	157.6°	22.4°	12.69		

Key: ND= Non-drivers; PD= Professional Drivers; NPD= Non-professional Drivers; SD= Standard Deviation; p= level of significance; AKE= Active Knee Extension

Hamstring Tightness * Less than 20°= Mild Hamstring Tightness Between 20°- 25°= Moderate Hamstring Tightness; Greater than 25°= Severe Hamstring Tightness

The result of Analysis of variance showed that there were significant differences in the hamstring muscle tightness of the Right lower extremity across the three groups (F= 19.410, P= 0.000). Similarly, there were significant differences in the hamstring muscle tightness of the left lower extremity (F= 22.617, p= 0.000) respectively (Table 14). The result of the Post Hoc Analysis showed that the right Active knee Extension (AKE) of the non-drivers was significantly higher than that of the professional drivers (p= 0.000). Also, the Active knee Extension (AKE) of the non-professional drivers was significantly higher than that

of the professional drivers (p = 0.015), (Table 15). However, the result of the Post Hoc Analysis of the Active knee Extension for Left showed that the Active knee Extension (AKE) of the non-drivers was significantly higher than that of the professional drivers (p= 0.000). However, there was no significant difference in the Active knee Extension (AKE) of the non-professional and professional drivers (p= 0.067), implicating that the non-professional and professional drivers had same degree of hamstring muscle tightness in the left lower limb (Table 15).

Table 14: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Comparing the Active knee Extension of the Right and Left Limbs Across the Groups

Hamstring	ANOVA	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	p-value
Right Tightness	Between Groups	3868.87	1934.43	19.41	0.00
	Within Groups	14550.76	99.66		
	Total	18419.63			
Left Tightness	Between Groups	5088.64	2544.32	22.61	0.00
	Within Groups	16536.86	112.49		
	Total	21625.50			

Key: AKERIGHT= Active knee Extension for the Right limb; AKELEFT= Active knee Extension for the Left limb; F= Frequency; p-value= level of significance

Table 15: Post Hoc Results Comparing the Active Knee Extension of the Right and Left Limbs Across the Groups

Hamstring	Groups(I)	Groups (J)	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	p-value
Right Tightness	1.00	2.00	12.36*	1.99	0.00
		3.00	7.41*	2.01	0.00
	2.00	1.00	-12.36*	1.99	0.00
		3.00	-4.95*	2.01	0.01
	3.00	1.00	-7.41*	2.01	0.00
		2.00	4.95*	2.01	0.01
Left Tightness	1.00	2.00	13.84*	2.12	0.00
		3.00	9.92*	2.12	0.00
	2.00	1.00	-13.84*	2.12	0.00
		3.00	-3.92*	2.12	0.07
	3.00	1.00	-9.92*	2.12	0.00
		2.00	3.92	2.12	0.06

Key: AKERIGHT= Active knee Extension for the Right limb; AKELEFT= Active knee Extension for the Left limb 1.00= Non-drivers; 2.00= Professional Drivers; 3.00= Non-professional Drivers; Std. Error= Standard Error; p-value= level of significance

Discussion

The results of this study showed high prevalence of hamstring tightness among professional drivers compared to non-drivers and non-professionals. The prevalence rates of hamstring muscle tightness were 78%, 54% and 16% among professional, non-professional drivers and non-drivers respectively. This finding lent credence to most reports in previous studies among related professions to driving. Sharma and Gupta (2021) in India, reported a prevalence of 74% in hamstring tightness among two-wheeler motorcycle riders [22]. Similarly, Mehreen *et al* (2021) reported that the prevalence rate of hamstring tightness among administrative staff was about 55% in Lahore, Pakistan [4]. In an old literature, Magnusson *et al* (1996) also reported an increase in musculoskeletal disorders among professional city bus drivers in Hong Kong [11]. We still considered the prevalence rate observed in this study to be high despite that it was lower than the rates of 82%, 85.7% and 96% reported among students, office workers and diamond sorters respectively

[25,13,26]. Furthermore, the current prevalence of hamstring muscle tightness finding was higher when compared to the report of Shakya and Manandhar [26], although, theirs was among physiotherapy students. Alberto *et al* (2023) reported that individuals with hamstring extensibility reduction has no differences in dynamic stability after landing nor agility after fatigue test, but significantly affects reaching distances during one-leg balance [23].

The value of the right Active knee Extension (AKE) of the non-drivers was significantly higher than that of the professional drivers, implying that the hamstring muscle tightness was significantly higher in the later. Similarly, the value of the AKE of the professional drivers was significantly lower than that of the non-professional drivers, which implied that the hamstring muscle tightness was higher in the former. However, the non-drivers had significantly lower hamstring muscle tightness compared to others. It was observed that there was no significant difference in the hamstring tightness of the non-professional and

professional drivers and this implied that the non-professional and professional drivers had same degree of hamstring muscle tightness in the left lower limb. It is noteworthy that the driving experience and sitting hours of the professional drivers were significantly higher than that of the non-professional drivers in the study. The professional drivers in this current study maintained sitting posture for an average of 13 hours compared to the non-professional drivers and non-drivers. The increased muscle tightness observed among professional drivers might be due to persistent isometric contraction of the hamstring in the sitting posture during driving for a long period of time.

Prolonged poor sitting posture had been reported to account for half of work-related musculoskeletal dysfunctions (MSD), leading to increased and continuous static load; stress and strain on the muscles, tendons, and ligaments with resultant pain and discomfort over time [27,28, 29, 30]. Significant association had also been reported between long sitting posture and work-related musculoskeletal dysfunctions in developed nations around the world [31]. Hamstring tightness have also been documented to affect performance[32].The clinical implication of this study is high with the high prevalence of hamstring tightness among the drivers, implying that they will have poor flexibility, with reductions in power, speed, and agility of the lower extremity during driving, hence, they are prone to injuries.

This study showed that there was no significant relationship between BMI and the prevalence of hamstring tightness; this corroborated the study among sewing machine workers where there was no relationship between hamstring tightness and BMI [33]. There are limited literatures on the relationship between BMI and hamstring tightness, however, a study conducted among young healthy individual showed a weak relationship between the two variables [34]. Efforts should be aimed at encouraging stretching exercises coupled with reducing prolonged sitting hours by stopping to stretch for few seconds during driving and also encourage appropriate ergonomic sitting position while driving.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the prevalence rates of hamstring muscle tightness were 78%, 54% and 16% among the professional, non-professional and non-drivers respectively. However, BMI is not a predisposing factor to hamstring tightness but long duration of sitting among drivers can be a contributory factor.

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